

Synthesis of some Newer Biologically Active Substituted-3-[(6-substituted-2-hydrazono)benzothiazolyl]-2-indolinones. Part-LIV

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5-Bromo- and 5-methyl-7-bromoisatins (1a) have been synthesised and transformed into the corresponding 1-methyl analogs (1b). 1a and 1b have been condensed with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles to yield 3 and 4. Mannich condensation of 3 using morpholine and piperidine furnished the corresponding 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl analogs (5). The compounds have been characterised by means of ir and pmr spectroscopy.

A survey of literature revealed that a number of isatin derivatives possess various biological properties¹. Moreover, benzothiazole derivatives exhibit a wide range of biological activities². In view of these observations we have synthesised several 3-[(6-substituted-2-hydrazono)benzothiazolyl]-2-indolinones in order to evaluate their anthelmintic activity.

2-Hydrazinobenzothiazoles (2) and 5-bromo- and 5-methyl-7-bromoisatins (1a) were prepared as shown in Scheme 1. Conversion of 5-bromo- and 5-methyl-7-bromoisatins to the corresponding 1-methyl derivatives (1b) was accomplished with dimethyl sulphate and ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution. Reactions of 2 as a nucleophile on 1a and 1b yielded 3 and 4, respectively, in good yields.

Treatment of 3 with morpholine/piperidine in presence of formaldehyde yielded 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-5-bromo-3-[(6-substituted-2-hydrazono)benzothiazolyl]-2-indolinones (5). Mannich condensation on 3 were supported by their correct elemental analysis. Ir spectra showed absorption bands at 1690–1710 (C=O) and 1590–1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The NH peak which was present in 3, was absent in the Mannich bases (5). The carbonyl absorption which appeared as a broad peak in 3 became very sharp in 5.

Mannich condensation failed on 3 (R''=5-Me-7-Br, R'=OMe, Cl, Me).

Experimental

Purity of the compounds was routinely checked by tlc. Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

5; R''=5-Br, 5a; R'=Cl, X=O. 5b; R'=Me, X=O.
5c; R'=OMe, X=O, 5d; R'=Cl, X=CH₃;
5e; R'=Me, X=OH, 5f; R'=OMe, X=CH₃.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) Concentrated HCl, Na₂SO₄, (ii) concentrated H₂SO₄, (iii) Me₂SO, KOH, EtOH, (iv) KSON, (v) Br₂, (vi) NH₂NH₂, H₂O, (vii) morpholine/piperidine, HCHO.

5-Methyl-7-bromo-satin (1a): To chloral hydrate (9 g) in water (120 ml) were added sodium sulphate (13 g), a solution of 2-bromo-4-methylaniline^s (5.4 g) (in 30 ml of water to which 4.3 ml of concentrated HCl was added to dissolve the amine) and a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (11 g) in water (50 ml). The mixture was heated over a wire gauze and vigorously boiled for 5 min and cooled. The resulting crystals of 2-bromo-4-methyl-isonitroso-acetanilide were filtered and dried, m.p. 190°.

To warm (60°) concentrated H₂SO₄ (40 ml; *d* 1.84) was added dry 2-bromo-4-methyl-isonitroso-acetanilide (5 g) at such a rate as to keep the temperature at 60–70°. The reaction mixture was then heated to 80° for about 14 min, cooled to room temperature and poured on crushed ice. After standing for about 0.5 h, the resulting solid was filtered, washed with cold water (3×10 ml) and the crude mass was suspended in hot water (100 ml) and treated with a solution of NaOH (3 g). A small quantity of dilute HCl was added to the solution until a slight precipitate was obtained. It was then filtered and the filtrate acidified with HCl to precipitate pure 5-methyl-7-bromoisatin which was filtered and dried, (70%), m.p. 180°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1732 (C=O), 1610 (C=C) and 3150 cm⁻¹ (NH).

1,5-Dimethyl-7-bromoisatin (1b): To a suspension of 5-methyl-7-bromoisatin (5 g) in ethanol (25 ml), ethanolic potassium hydroxide (25 ml; 10%) was added dropwise for 20 min with shaking. To the resulting deep purple solution freshly distilled dimethyl sulphate (4 ml) was added and the mixture stirred for 30 min and then filtered. The excess ethanol was distilled off and the solution cooled to yield **1b** as orange needles (60%), m.p. 152°; δ (CDCl₃) 2.2 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.5 (s, N-CH₃), 7.25 (s, Ar-4-H) and 7.4 (Ar-6-H).

5-Bromo-3-[(6-chloro-2-hydrazono)benzothiazolyl]-2-indolinone (3a): A suspension of 5-bromoisatin (2.4 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (25 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) was heated on a water-bath. **2a** (1.89 g, 0.01 mol) was then added to it and heating continued for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid filtered and washed with methanol (2×5 ml) to yield the product (Table 1).

1-Methyl-5-bromo-3-[(6-substituted-2-hydrazono)benzothiazolyl]-2-indolinone (4): The compounds were prepared in a similar manner using 1-methyl-5-bromoisatin and **2** (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SUBSTITUTED-3-[(6-SUBSTITUTED-2-HYDRAZONO)BENZOTHAZOLYL]-2-INDOLINONES

Compd. no.	R'	R	R*	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analyses % (Found)/(Calcd.)	
							O	H
3a	5-Br	Cl	H	>260	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ BrClN ₄ O ₂ S	49.7 (44.1)	2.5 (1.9)
3b	5-Br	Me	H	>265	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₂ S	49.8 (49.6)	3.3 (2.8)
3c	5-Br	OMe	H	>261	71	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	47.1 (47.6)	3.2 (2.7)
3d	5-Me-7-Br	Cl	H	>260	79	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ BrClN ₄ O ₂ S	45.3 (45.5)	2.2 (2.8)
3e	5-Me-7-Br	Me	H	>260	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₂ S	50.4 (50.8)	3.1 (3.2)
3f	5-Me-7-Br	OMe	H	>255	84	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	48.6 (48.9)	3.4 (3.1)
4a	5-Br	Cl	Me	>260	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ BrClN ₄ O ₂ S	45.8 (45.5)	2.7 (2.3)
4b	5-Br	Me	Me	>260	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₂ S	50.7 (50.8)	3.3 (3.2)
4c	5-Br	OMe	Me	>270	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	48.7 (48.9)	3.4 (3.1)
4d	5-Me-7-Br	Cl	Me	>250	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ BrClN ₄ O ₂ S	47.2 (46.8)	3.2 (2.7)
4e	5-Me-7-Br	Me	Me	240	77	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₂ S	52.2 (52.0)	3.4 (3.6)
4f	5-Me-7-Br	OMe	Me	>265	88	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	50.0 (50.1)	3.0 (3.4)
5a	5-Br	Cl	MM	210	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BrClN ₄ O ₂ S	47.8 (47.8)	3.8 (3.8)
5b	5-Br	Me	MM	180	75	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ BrN ₄ O ₂ S	51.4 (51.8)	4.4 (4.1)
5c	5-Br	OMe	MM	225	75	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	49.8 (50.2)	4.2 (4.0)
5d	5-Br	Cl	PM	240	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ BrClN ₄ O ₂ S	49.4 (49.9)	3.3 (3.7)
5e	5-Br	Me	PM	165	75	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ BrN ₄ O ₂ S	55.0 (54.5)	4.1 (4.6)
5f	5-Br	OMe	PM	182–83	85	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	52.3 (52.8)	4.7 (4.4)

*MM = Morpholinomethyl; PM = piperidinomethyl.

1-Morpholino | piperidinomethyl-5-bromo-3-[(6-substituted-2-hydrazono)benzothiazolyl]-2-indolinones (5): To a boiling clear solution of **3** (0.003 mol) in DMF-methanol (10 ml), formaldehyde solution (0.5 ml) and morpholine/piperidine (0.5 ml) were added and the mixture was heated on a water-bath with stirring for ~ 10 min. The contents were allowed to remain at room temperature overnight. The resulting fluffy orange coloured solid was recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) to yield the product; **5a**, δ (CDCl₃), 2.65 (4H, m, N(CH₂)₂), 3.7 (4H, s, (CH₂)₂), 4.48 (2H, s, NCH₂N) and 6.81-7.76 (m, ArH, NH); *m/e* 505/507 (*M*⁺), 405/407, 377/379, 298/300, 168 and 100; **5b** 1.55 (m, (CH₂)₂), 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.62 (4H, t, N(CH₂)₂), 3.7 (4H, t, O(CH₂)₂), 4.48 (2H, s, NCH₂N) and 6.9-7.75 (m, ArH, NH); *m/e* 485/487 (*M*⁺), 385/387, 357/359, 197/199 and 100; **5c** 1.5 (m, (CH₂)₂), 2.4 (3H, m, CH₃), 2.60 (m, 4H, N(CH₂)₂), 4.48 (2H, s, NCH₂N) and 6.8-7.6 (ArH, NH); *m/e* 501/503 (*M*⁺), 401/403, 373/375, 294, 179, 164, 134 and 100; **5d** 2.58 (4H, m, N(CH₂)₂), 4.48 (2H, s, NCH₂N) and 6.91-7.75 (m, ArH, NH); *m/e* 503/505 (*M*⁺ not seen), 405/407, 377/379, 298/300 and 98.

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